

Tool 1

Identify your research question: guiding questions

Welcome to the Citizen Science Starter Kit.

This template is part of Module 4 “Getting started with citizen science” (phase 0 – consider), which helps you to identify a research question for citizen science. Some helpful tips are provided to help you formulate a strong research question.

Please download this template to your own folder and fill it in on your local computer. If you have any further questions about this template, please contact citizenscience@vub.be.

1. What are current themes of interest? What are current concerns of the public?

Tip: A good research question should aim to contribute to an existing debate in your field, or in society at large. Start from issues that are related to citizens’ interests and concerns. You can identify pressing questions by accessing the database of the Science Shop ([‘Wetenschapswinkel’](#)), or by organising participatory research methods (e.g. crowdsourcing, mapping tools, etc.). You can also consult the (grey) literature and talk to experts in the field.

Write your findings in the text box below:

2. What is the underlying problem or issue that needs to be solved?

Tip: Once you have gained a better understanding about citizens’ interests and concerns, the next step is to formulate a problem statement. A problem statement is a short, clear explanation about the issue or challenge that you want to change. A strong problem statement is focused on a single problem or issue. Describe the underlying problem or issue in one single paragraph in the text box below, with the help of the following elements: current state, desired state, and magnitude of the problem:

3. Which gaps did you find in the literature that help you to frame your research question?

Tip: The research question should be original enough, with the potential to provide new scientific or broader socio-economic impacts. Have a look at the literature and map existing projects in your research fields by exploring inventories of citizen science hubs, such as <https://eu-citizen.science/>.

Write your findings in the text box below:

4. What are the timeframe and geographical boundaries of the problem?

Tip: Teamwork makes the dream work! Citizen science is highly suitable for research questions that have a large spatial or temporal scope. By engaging a large group of citizen scientists at the same time, the research can be more effectively accomplished. The time and costs needed to perform the same job by more conventional science methods differ considerably. Nevertheless, citizen science projects with a small spatial and temporal scale are also possible.

Describe the envisioned temporal and spatial scale in the text box below:

5. Who is affected by the problem?

Tip: You need to have a good idea about the profile of the participants in citizen science and have the necessary time and efforts available to involve them in the research (project). Citizen science can reach large audiences, but you can also decide to keep it simple with only a few participants.

Write a first list of potential target groups of your research (project) in the text box below:

